

Short Communication

Technology Addiction among Teenagers

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Abstract

Technology development is increasing every single day. This fact pace of technological development effects our lives in many different ways. We can see that in all domains our lives are becoming more digital. Especially with the augmentation of cell phones and internet people benefit the technology on daily bases. Teenagers are the most technology contacted which makes them more under danger of technology addiction. Despite all the benefits of technology, unconscious use of it may cause severe health problems both mental and physical. Studies show that use of technology and technology based education system in classrooms may cause students to be technology addicts. It is more beneficial that technology is used in an efficient and reasonable way so that students can do their learning without distractions. To prevent this, it is highly important that students, teachers and parents are well educated about technology use so that, they would be aware of a technology addiction situation.

Keywords: Technology, Addiction, Teenagers, Health problems, Social problems

1 Introduction

We are in touch with technology in nearly every single moment of our lives. We live an online and a digital life that eases a lot of the work that we used to do. People from every generation and nation uses technological advances on daily bases for different purposes but with the same motive which is making life easier. Technology addiction is increasingly continuing due to its easy access and entertaining nature. (Greenfield, 1999; Young, 2010). This high demand and attention on technology drives technological development companies to produce something new every single day and this augments the speed of development the technology. Increasing development of technology and unconscious use of it causes more damage than its benefits. Internet addiction is considered to be a clinical disorder and it needs to be treated under professional conditions. (Young, 2010). This augmentation of technological developments vastly effects both the educational life and social life of teenagers. Technology use in the domain of education may cause many risks which are often ignored. Every educator must consider the benefits and disadvantages of technology integrated education before combining them. (Spitzer, 2014). The fact that technological devices and internet is easily obtainable and reachable makes the addiction even more frequent. The amount of damage caused by technology addiction including mental health problems and physical problems such as obesity is

increasing day by day. According to a study several mental disorders generally comorbid with IVGA (investigated internet and video game addiction) and IGD (internet gaming disorder). During another study which was made with 330 Korean middle school students, 20% of those with IGD identified with psychiatric comorbidity. When we take a look at the psychiatric diseases comorbitted by technology addiction, we can identify depressive disorders, which show the most comorbidity with IGD and IVGA. It's also shown that ADHD, impulsivity and autism spectrum disorders (ASD), in this study 22% of patients suffering from ADHD was also suffering from IVGA as well. Following these serious mental and physical diseases it is fairly difficult to predict the moment of addiction as a technology user. (Susman, 2018) Seeing that technology and digital development is an area that is growing in a very fast pace, it quite difficult and risky to try to adapt it into teenage education system. Is it possible that technology use in classrooms may cause post-school technology addiction problems? Studies shows some danger signals about this subject and pushes us to reconsider the technology integration to teenage school education system. (Spitzer, 2014). We face the necessity of technology use education, if we want technology integrated education system during adolescent years of students. Another important point is that education should not be limited with school but it also should be followed by a home education which requires parent that are aware of technology use. Parents and teachers should be aware of the damage that technology addiction may cause and they should know what they should do under an addiction situation. Shortly, while the technology is developing,

it is important that we consider the benefits and damages that technology might cause. It is also important that adults around teenagers like parents and teachers, who have a very important effect on their lives because of the amount of time that teenagers spend with them, are more aware of technology use and its possible consequences.

2 Methods

Technology and internet addiction are rapidly increasing everywhere in the world. Our goal with this study is to review the studies that have been made so far about technology and internet addiction. In addition to that we also would like to demonstrate and view the mental and physical effects of this addiction on teenagers with this study we aimed to compare studies that were made in our country and other global studies. Another goal of ours was to compare the programs that were prepared to fight against technology and internet addiction globally. We have viewed the results and the damage that internet addiction may have cause in the future. We aimed to create a synthesis of different studies about this subject in which technological development is considered to cause technology addiction, specifically among teenagers in different areas.

3 Results

Nowadays, the use of internet and technology is widely popular and with the development of mobile phone use, it has a more important role in our lives. 40% of the world's population is using internet and during the past 10 years it is shown that internet use has augmented 6 times more. This study reports the presence of addiction for internet (1.3%–2% males and 0.6% females) and cell phone (4.1%–2.5% males and 1.5% females) (Sharma 2017)

When we take a look to the studies that were made in our country, we can see a rate of 10% technology addiction.(Gunuc,2010).When we look at the studies that were made by Çam and his colleagues, pathological internet use is shown to be 7,1%(Çam, 2015). In another research 2.33% of people that were studied were found to be technology addicted and the other 17,45% was in under the risk group.(Gokcearslan, 2012) When we look to the studies that were made globally, children who are shown to be pathological internet users between ages 13-18 has more anxiety, depression and obesity problems compared to those who are normal internet users.. (Cam, 2015) In another research 2.33% of people that were studied were found to be technology addicted and the other 17,45% was in under the risk group.(Gokcearslan, 2012)

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DISCUSSION

Overuse of digital technologies is considered as a public health problem. (WHO, 2014)

Digital media creates serious risks and side effects when used in educational environments. It is particularly striking when used for extracurricular activities. Children are distracted by stealing

their learning time. In general, it seems to be not beneficial to learning behaviors. Children in pre-school education are the weakest against digital education and technology dependence, and their effects continue to have no effect even after school.

The use of computers in small children, mistakes, also affects older age education. Because of this reason, young children should be given information about side effects as well as education on computer use. Education at this early age on the use of information and palace use and information and computer addiction will affect older age-related technology dependence and education. (Spitzer, 2014)

Emphasis is placed on technology dependency in the work being done. The relation between technology dependence and both malfunctioning gambling and alcohol use disorders has been examined. As a result, problematic gambling has a stronger relationship with information technology addiction than alcohol use disorder. The study is interpreted as a set of disorders in which technology dependency is not solely a problem but belongs to different dependencies. Findings also show that information technology dependency is more similar to other behavioral dependencies than drug addiction. (Sigerson, 2017)

Treatment is required to manage problematic technological behaviors. It is recommended that trainees collaborate to provide a consensus on diagnostic criteria and measures in order to improve the credibility of studies and to develop effective and efficient treatment approaches for treatment seekers. This will also contribute to providing an incentive for public policy and health care providers to provide financing for those in need of professional assistance. As a result, research and clinical initiatives should focus on providing the best possible care for individuals suffering from severe disruption and distress as a consequence of their internet use. (Kuss, 2016)

Unconscious technology use and internet addiction causes both mental and physical damage. Such as obesity, depression and anxiety(Cam, 2015).

Internet addiction shows a direct proportion within the teenagers who suffer from obesity and mental disorders wich is a risk factor to depression and anxiety. (Wei, 2017)

Studies Show that there are very few precautions or programs that are prepared to fight against technology addiciton before it shows up. It is important that people start to take severe measures to both decrease the time consumed anad the financial lost caused to schools and medşcal centers by this addiction. .(Bagatarhan, 2017 ;Çam, 2015;Şenorman,2010;Köse,2016). Because technology addiction is so commonly seen among teenagers, based on their integrity with digital world in every aspect of their life, it is necessary that parents, teachers and teenagers are educated under certain topics that connect with efficient technology use and addiction.

Treatment options for diseases that were caused by technology addiction and unconscious technology use is increasing every single day. Despite all the work that was put through the war against internet addiction, the results are still not clear for us. For example

for higher education students TDI(Technology delivered intervention) method is still not a clear and effective solution for a precaution. (Conley, 2016)

When education is getting digitalized, this may cause some problems that should be considered before. Student may find technology devices that were provided for educational reasons as a source of entertainment, which will eventually distract them from the course work. Technological devices in a classroom may steal the valuable time where they should be learning from the students, instead they use these devices as a source of entertainment. We can see that there are not enough benefits of technology into students grades or class performance.

Preschool education students are most the most vulnerable group to technology addiction. As they grow up, they may see the results of the damage that was done years ago, even during after school periods. Among younger children and teenagers, wrong use of technology highly affects the future education periods. Because of the stated reasons it is considerably important that both students and families are educated about technology use and technology addiction. Technology education at a younger age will affect the future addiction life of the person. (Spitzer, 2014)

Rapid development of technology in the world brings convenience in our daily life, excessive and unconscious use leads to health problems such as psychopathological, physical symptoms and obesity in children and adolescents. I have prepared a review by examining the relationship between technology development in the domain of education and increasing obesity. I have analyzed studies from all over the world to see the relevance between the technological education system and the health problems and social problems that many students suffer from. After analyzing papers and comparing the amount of virtuality the education system has gained and the augmentation of addiction among teens it is observed that despite all the advantages that technological education system provided it also created an uncontrolled environment where the young students can easily become technology addicts. The significant amount of relevance between the technological education system and the emerging health issues followed by an antisocial behavior demonstrates that it is necessary that we start considering the damage that our youth and society has taken because of the developing technology integration in education. The main reason that I want to study on this subject is that the education world is getting more and more virtual every day, that it is predicted that the student won't be obligated to go to school and they will be able to self-educate themselves at home or get their education from virtual teachers, and our society couldn't catch up with the rapidness of this new educational system that we don't know how to benefit of this system and instead we harm ourselves. It is very important that students are aware of the amount of usage of technology and virtual platforms in education. It is believed that virtualizing the education will develop the educational system but usage of this technology is often unconscious. To eliminate and minimize these destructive aspects of technological development in the domain of education it is necessary that students, parents and teachers should be educated in the usage of technology so that they will be more integrated with the field that they will be more aware of their behaviors toward virtuality.

Conflict of Interest: no

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